

Quantum Calculus ($q = e^h$) and the Symmetrized Radioactive Decay Law

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Abstract

The radioactive decay law was first formulated by Ernest Rutherford and Frederick Soddy in 1902. As a well-known law, one of its primary applications is to determine the dates of ancient specimens. The process is known as radiocarbon dating and is subjected to the known properties of radioactive nuclei. In this paper, we implement quantum calculus ($q = e^h$) to express the solution of the radioactive decay equation in symmetrized q -exponential form. Also, we explore the q -analog of the decay constant using Tsallis logarithmic function for various miscellaneous q -values. Furthermore, the factor-label method was applied to our analysis to show that the correct units remained intact under the application of quantum calculus. In conclusion, we showed that a variation of the q -parameter was akin to the production of a new isotope $\forall q \in (0, 1)$.

Keywords: q -calculus, radioactive decay, half-life, factor-label method

1 Introduction

1.1 Classical decay

A known solution to the radioactive decay equation can be yielded from an elementary technique in ordinary differential equations known as the separation of variables[1]. Of course, this is not the only method to solve such an equation. Another method which ensures an identical solution to the previous equation is the power series method. However, if we let the initial conditions of our system be as follows: at time $t = 0$, $N(t) = N_o = a_o$. Then the solution by the power series method is determined by substituting Eq.(1.2) in Eq.(1.1) to give Eq.(1.3),

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -\lambda N \quad (1.1)$$

$$N(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} a_n t^n \quad (1.2)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} (n+1)a_{n+1}t^n + \lambda \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} a_n t^n = 0. \quad (1.3)$$

The terms a_n and a_{n+1} are related and hence the power series[6] solution is attained by substituting a_n in Eq.(1.2) where,

$$a_n = \frac{(-1)^n (\lambda)^n}{n!} a_0 \quad (1.4)$$

and

$$N(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} \frac{(-1t)^n (\lambda)^n}{n!} a_0. \quad (1.5)$$

A quicker and perhaps more straightforward method to find the solution to Eq.(1.1) is by separating variables[11]. The terms N_0 , $N(t)$, λ , and t are: (i) the number of nuclei at $t = 0$, (ii) the number of nuclei at $t > 0$, (iii) the radioactive decay constant, and (iv) the time t , respectively. Additionally, if we integrate Eq.(1.1) using the method of separation of variables, we get

$$\int_{N_0}^{N(t)} \frac{dN}{N} = -\lambda \int_0^t dt \quad (1.6)$$

$$\boxed{N = N_0 \exp(-\lambda t)}. \quad (1.7)$$

1.2 Quantum calculus

Quantum calculus[3] or sometimes called q -calculus is calculus done without limits. The term h in $q = e^h$ is used as a reminder of the planckian constant, while the term q stands for "quantum". In the limit $h \rightarrow 0$, $q \rightarrow 1$ and the classical form of calculus is recovered[10]. Furthermore, another important concept in q -calculus which will be discussed later in more detail, is the derivative and its q -analog (it is important to point out that currently no q -analog for the generalized chain rule exist [10]). Moreover, the downward arrow between Eqs.(1.8) and (1.9) illustrates the removal of the limit, which is replaced by the number "1" and hence,

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{qx - x} \quad (1.8)$$

↓

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \left\{ 1 \right\} \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{qx - x}. \quad (1.9)$$

2 q -Basics

2.1 The q -integer

Definition 2.1. Given that $0 < q < 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the q -integer is defined by:

$$[n]_q = \begin{cases} \frac{1-q^n}{1-q}, & \text{if } q \neq 1, \\ n, & \text{if } q = 1, \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

for $q \in \mathbb{R}[4]$.

2.2 The q -factorial

Definition 2.2. Let $0 < q < 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then the q -factorial[4] is defined as follows:

$$[n]_q! = \begin{cases} [n]_q [n-1]_q \dots [1]_q, & n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \\ 1, & n = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

2.3 Tsallis q -logarithm

Definition 2.3. Let q be a real parameter defined on the open interval $(0, 1)$ [17], then the Tsallis q -logarithm [4] is defined by:

$$\ln_q(x) = \begin{cases} \ln(x), & x > 0, \text{ and } q = 1, \\ \frac{x^{1-q} - 1}{1-q}, & x > 0, \text{ and } q \neq 1, \\ \text{undefined}, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Therefore, using **def 2.3**, we conveniently show that in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$, $\ln_q(x)$ goes to:

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{\ln_q(x)\} = (-1) \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} (x^{1-q}) \quad (2.4)$$

and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{\ln_q(x)\} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{du} (e^{u \cdot \ln(x)}) = \ln(x), \quad (2.5)$$

where we have made the substitution ($u = 1 - q$), in Eq.(14).

2.4 The q -derivative

Definition 2.4. Let $f(x)$ be a function that is differentiable and hence continuous; then its q -derivative [5] is define by:

$$(D_q f)(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(qx)}{(1 - q)x}, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (2.6)$$

where q in quantum calculus is described as the so-called q -parameter and varies strictly between 0 and 1.

Clearly, from **Def. 2.4**, in the limit that $q \rightarrow 1$,

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (D_q f)(x) = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \quad (2.7)$$

and we recover the classical form of the derivative. Likewise, following from the definition of the q -derivative[12], for constants α and β there exist a linear relationship such that:

$$\begin{aligned} D_q \{ \alpha f(x) + \beta g(x) \} \\ = \alpha D_q \{ f(x) \} + \beta D_q \{ g(x) \}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

The next formula we shall consider is the product rule. In classical calculus, given the product of two functions ($f(x) * g(x)$)—the derivative can be applied to the first function while holding the second function followed by an addition sign and then the derivative is applied to second function while holding the first function. Therefore, we will show that the product rule in q -calculus is nearly identical to its counterpart in classical calculus. The only difference between them is the q -parameter appears in the argument of the first function, i.e., $f(x)$ becomes $f(qx)$ and the q -derivative operates on each individual function as it would in classical calculus. Henceforth, using Eqs. (2.6) and (2.8), we may write the product formula for $x \neq 0$

as:

$$\begin{aligned} D_q \{ f(x)g(x) \} &= \\ &= \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(x)g(x)}{(q - 1)x} \\ &= \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(qx)g(x)}{(q - 1)x} \\ &\quad + \frac{f(qx)g(x) - f(x)g(x)}{(q - 1)x} \\ &= \frac{f(qx)(g(qx) - g(x))}{(q - 1)x} \\ &\quad + \frac{(f(qx) - f(x))g(x)}{(q - 1)x} \\ &= f(qx)D_q g(x) \\ &\quad + D_q f(x)g(x). \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

In like manner, the quotient rule and a non-generalized example that leads to a limited definition of the chain rule-no generalized chain rule currently exist—are given by[10],

$$\begin{aligned} D_q \left\{ \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right\} &= \\ &= \frac{1}{(q - 1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(qx)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} \right\} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(q - 1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{g(qx)} \left\{ \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{(q - 1)x} \right\} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(q - 1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(x)g(x) - f(x)g(qx)}{g(qx)g(x)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{g(qx)} D_q f(x) \\ &\quad + \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)g(x)} \left\{ \frac{g(x) - g(qx)}{(q - 1)x} \right\} \\ &= \frac{g(x)D_q f(x) - f(x)D_q g(x)}{g(qx)g(x)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

and for an arbitrary function of the form $f(u(x)) = f(\alpha x^\beta)$ [10], where α and β are constants, we get the following equation for

a special case of the chain rule[18],

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\{f(u(x))\} &= \\
D_q\{f(\alpha x^\beta)\} &= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta} \times \frac{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta}{(q-1)x} \\
&= (D_{q^\beta} f)(u(x)) D_q(u(x)). \quad (2.11)
\end{aligned}$$

2.5 The q -exponential

Definition 2.5. The q -exponential function (with $q \in (0, 1)$) is defined by

$$e_q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{[n]_q!}. \quad (2.12)$$

It should be obvious (from **Def. 2.2**) that the classical exponential function (e^x) is recovered in the limit as q approaches one. The term in the denominator of Eq.(2.12), $[n]_q! = [1]_q[2]_q \dots [n]_q$ [7] is the only major difference between e^x and $e_q(x)$ and this is where the symmetry and invariance arises from, when $q \rightarrow \frac{1}{q}$ and $[n]_q = \frac{q^n - q^{-n}}{q - q^{-1}}$, hence $e_q(x) = e_{\frac{1}{q}}(x)$ ¹. Again, the fact that in the limiting case one can recover the classical form makes quantum calculus exceptionally beautiful[19].

3 q -Deformed decay

3.1 Deformed decay

The precursory definition of the q -exponential function in section (2.5) will enable us to write the solution for the radioactive decay equation by means of a suitable power series[2]. Notice that within the solution-Eq.(1.7)-the radioactive decay constant λ is still present, as should be. Subsequently, this constant will be written in

¹A redefinition of $[n]_q$ suffices $e_q(x) = e_{\frac{1}{q}}(x)$ to be completely symmetric, hence $[N]_q(t)$ is symmetric.

terms of Tsallis q -logarithm. It will then be shown graphically-if we let the q -parameter vary for values strictly between 0 and 1 [14], that the classical form is indeed recovered whenever $q \rightarrow 1$. We are able to achieve this by choosing a known isotope of oxygen (oxygen-22) with a corresponding half-life of 2.25 seconds. The choice of isotope is completely random, and there exist no reason why any other isotope with a known half-life would not serve the same purpose. The modified decay constant is the given by:

$$\lambda_q = \frac{1}{2.25s} \times \ln_q(2). \quad (3.1)$$

Let the power series for $N(t)$ be defined as was shown in Eq. (1.2), then

$$\frac{d_q N(t)}{d_q t} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n t^{n-1}. \quad (3.2)$$

Now given that $[0]_q = 0$, then

$$\frac{d_q N(t)}{d_q t} = [0]_q a_0 t^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n t^{n-1} \quad (3.3)$$

for $n \geq 1$. We then substitute Eq.(3.3) in Eq.(1.1) and this gives,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n+1]_q a_{n+1} t^n + \lambda \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n t^n = 0. \quad (3.4)$$

The terms in Eq. (3.4), which are of the form a_n and a_{n+1} [8] are the coefficients of t^n , therefore we must equate them, which gives

$$a_{n+1} = -\frac{\lambda a_n}{[n+1]_q}. \quad (3.5)$$

The relationship between a_n and a_{n+1} allows us to generate the following terms:

$$a_1 = -\frac{\lambda a_0}{[1]_q}; \quad (3.6)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q}; \quad (3.7)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q}; \quad (3.8)$$

$$a_4 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q}; \quad (3.9)$$

$$a_5 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q[5]_q}; \quad (3.10)$$

$$a_6 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q[5]_q[6]_q}. \quad (3.11)$$

Given that,

$$[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q \dots [n]_q = [n]_q! \quad (3.12)$$

we may write a_n as,

$$a_n = \frac{(-1)^n \lambda^n a_0}{[n]_q!}. \quad (3.13)$$

We may now substitute a_n in Eq.(1.2), giving us

$$N_q(t) = N_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \lambda^n t^n}{[n]_q!}, \quad (3.14)$$

and

$$\boxed{N_q(t) = N_0 e_q(-\lambda t)} \quad (3.15)$$

which is the q -analog of the symmetrized radioactive decay law. As a result of $e_q(x) = e_{\frac{1}{q}}(x)$, $N_{\frac{1}{q}}(t) = N_q(t)$ must be symmetric whenever $[n]_q = \frac{q^n - q^{-n}}{q - q^{-1}}$.

3.2 The Half-life

The half-life ($t_{1/2}$) is the time it takes for the number of radioactive nuclei to decrease by half the original value [13]. In the classical form, it is written as

$$\boxed{t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}} \quad (3.16)$$

where λ is the radioactive constant. The fact that $\ln_q(x)$ exist for $x > 0$ and $q \neq 1$,

we may write $t_{1/2}$ as $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{\lambda_q}$, where $t_{(1/2)Oxy22}$ is the Half-Life of oxygen-22. Again, we can move in the reverse direction to recover the classical form when $q \rightarrow 1$ as depicted below in Eq. (3.17),

$$\begin{aligned} t_{1/2} &= \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{t_{(1/2)Oxy22}\} \\ &= -\lambda^{-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} \left\{ 2^{1-q} \right\} \\ &= \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

Ultimately, we complete our task with plots of the form $\tilde{e}_q(\ln_q(x))$ (a property of Tsallis functions)², for several miscellaneous q -values.

3.3 q -Exponential plots

The values we utilized for the q -exponential plots are related to the q -parameter $\forall q \in (0, 1)$ [15]. We selected q -values of: 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.7, and 0.9 respectively. These values were substituted in the Tsallis q -logarithm- λ_q -and the numerical answers were divided by the half-life of oxygen-22 which is approximately 2.25 seconds (see **Table. 1**). The final result is substituted into $\tilde{e}_q(-\lambda_q t)$ and plotted for values of $t = [0, 20]$, since $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{\lambda_q}$.

Table 1: Miscellaneous q -values

q	$\frac{x^{1-q}-1}{1-q}$	$\left\{ \frac{x^{1-q}-1}{1-q} \right\} / t_{(1/2)Oxy22}(s^{-1})$
0.1	0.962	0.428
0.2	0.926	0.412
0.3	0.892	0.396
0.7	0.770	0.342
0.9	0.718	0.319

²This is just a representation of the inverse function from Tsallis statistics.

The exponential plots in Fig. 1 exhibit a remarkably simple idea that is in alignment with the initial ansatz (the classical form should be recovered in the limiting case). As the q -parameter is varied, for example, when $q = 0.1$ (red) the exponential plot decays faster than the other plots. On the contrary, for $q = 0.9$ (black) the decay is slower. This suggests that as $q \rightarrow 0$ radioactive decay occurs faster. In words, faster decays correspond to more intense radiation[9], which was observed in our plots. Finally, it is clear from our plots that a variation in the q -parameter (as $q \rightarrow 0$) has the effect of increasing the radioactive intensity. In contrast, as $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical form of the radioactive law is recovered.

Figure 1: q -exponential plots

4 Factor-label method

4.1 Unit-factor method

In this section, we applied the factor-label method (unit-factor method) to confirm that the units of our model are invariant under a variation of the q -parameter. The classical form of the radioactive law has the following units:

$$N(t) = N_0 * [scalar] \quad (4.1)$$

$$(nuclei) = (nuclei) * [scalar]. \quad (4.2)$$

A comparison of Eqs.(4.1) and (4.3) indicates the units are in agreement for the classical and quantum case (Eq.4.3)

$$\boxed{N_q(t) = N_o e_q(-\lambda t)}. \quad (4.3)$$

Also, for the exponent

$$\lambda t = t * \frac{\ln(2)}{t_{(1/2)}} \quad (4.4)$$

which is the classical form—the units are

$$1 * s^{-1} * s = [scalar] \quad (4.5)$$

where $\underbrace{1}$ represents the dimensionless nature of the logarithmic function. Now, in terms of the radioactive decay constant, the units for the Tsallis function also remained intact (Eqs. 4.5 and 4.7 have identical units), since

$$\boxed{\lambda_q t = \frac{\ln_q(2) * t}{t_{(1/2)Oxy22}}} \quad (4.6)$$

and,

$$s * s^{-1} = \frac{s * 1}{s} = [scalar]. \quad (4.7)$$

5 Conclusion

5.1 Concluding remarks

We have shown in our analysis, that by using a suitable power series it is possible to write the q -analog for the radioactive decay law. Additionally, we extended our analysis and showed that the radioactive decay constant can be written in terms of its q -analog while the units remained invariant in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$. Furthermore, we generated some plots to strengthen our analysis for several miscellaneous q -values, in particular $q = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.7$ and 0.9 . After analyzing the plots (**Fig. 1**), we found that as $q \rightarrow 0$, the decay process occurred at a faster rate. In other words, the radioactive decay intensity increased.

On the contrary, as $q \rightarrow 1$ the plots approached the classical form of the law. For $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = 2.25$ seconds and

$$\lambda_q = \left\{ \frac{x^{1-q} - 1}{1 - q} \right\} / t_{(1/2)Oxy22}, \quad (5.1)$$

a variation in the q -parameter is akin to the production of new isotopes. This is synonymous with a phenomenon in nuclear physics known as isotopic transmutation—since each isotope has its own characteristic radioactive decay constant. Note, that while the half-life of the isotope (oxygen-22) remained constant $\ln_q(2)$ changed $\forall q \in (0, 1)$ [16].

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